

Grain yield and other plant characters of a ratoon crop of IR9784-52-2-3-2 as affected by different rates and methods of N placement. IRRI, 1981 dry season (av of 4 replications).^a

Rate and method of placement	Grain (g/plant)	Panicles (no./plant)	Field grains (no./panicle)	Sterility (%)	100-grain weight (g)	Nodal tillers (%)	Plant height (cm)	Plant vigor ^b	Grain-straw ratio	Growth duration (days)
30 mg N/kg soil broadcast	9.2 b	18 b	32	24	1.89	74.9	69.9	7 a	1.2	58
30 mg N/kg soil deep placement	10.8 c	19 b	34	18	1.85	76.9	69.2	6 a	1.2	58
50 mg N/kg soil broadcast	16.9 b	25 ab	36	21	1.88	80.5	75.6	2 b	1.2	59
50 mg N/kg soil deep placement	25.1 a	34 a	39	13	1.87	65.7	75.2	1 b	1.0	61
Control	7.6 c	16 b	29	19	1.88	63.9	88.8	8 a	1.0	58
F-test on planned comparison										
Control vs others	**	ns	ns		ns	ns	ns	**	ns	ns
Broadcast vs deep placement	**	ns	ns		ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns

^a In a column, means followed by a common letter do not significantly differ at the 5% level. ^b 1 = extra vigorous; 3 = vigorous, 5 = intermediate or normal vigor, 7 = less vigorous than normal, 9 = very weak and small.

Effect of different sources and levels of nitrogen fertilizers on rice grain yield

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A field experiment was conducted on a loamy sand soil (pH 8.3, organic carbon 0.55%, electrical conductivity 0.05 mmho/cm) in Gurdaspur District of Punjab State to determine optimum nitrogen source and fertilizer rate for irrigated rice. Calcium ammonium nitrate, ammonium chloride, and urea were applied at 60, 120, and 180 kg N/ha. Each was applied in 3 equal splits: before puddling, and at 21 and 42 days after transplanting. Farming methods recommended for the area were followed and grain yield

Effect of N levels and sources on grain yield of rice variety IR8, Punjab, India.

N (kg/ha)	Rice yield (t/ha)			
	Calcium ammonium nitrate	Ammonium chloride	Urea	Mean
60	4.3	4.7	4.8	4.6
120	6.3	7.0	6.9	6.7
180	6.9	7.8	7.3	7.3
Mean	5.9	6.5	6.3	
	No nitrogen = 2.70			
	CD (5%)			
	Level or source = 0.28; level × source = 0.46.			
	Control × treatment = 0.45			

was recorded (see table).

Increasing N level significantly increased grain yield. Ammonium chloride produced maximum yield followed by

urea and calcium ammonium nitrate.

Calcium ammonium nitrate was significantly inferior to ammonium chloride and urea. □

Evaluation of nitrogen availability indices for rice in alluvial soils

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Different methods of testing soil nitrogen levels and their relationship to rice yields in alluvial soils were evaluated in the greenhouse. Five 20-day-old PR106 seedlings grown in a nitrogen-deficient solution culture were transplanted into pots, each with 4.5 kg surface soil (0-15 cm), from 20 Punjab soil sites. Soil pH varied from 7.2 to 10 and electrical conductivity from 0.15 to 2.12 mmho/cm. Treatments of 0 and 100 ppm N as urea

Indices of available nitrogen and their relationship with rice plant parameters.

	O. C. (%)	KMnO ₄ -N	NH ₄ ⁺ -N	NO ₃ ⁻ -N	NH ⁺ + NO ₃ ⁻ -N	NH ₄ ⁺ -N ^a
			<i>Available nitrogen (kg/ha)</i>			
Range	0.07-0.78	62.7-207.0	5.4-81.5	3.1-75.3	8.5-156.8	9.4-100.4
Mean	0.44	128.5	25.5	34.5	60.0	46.4
			<i>Correlation coefficients (r value)</i>			
Control grain yield	0.473	0.649	0.132	0.228	0.196	0.515
Percent grain yield	-0.027	0.143	0.159	0.193	0.169	0.004
Control grain uptake	0.433	0.581	0.261	0.288	0.313	0.489
Percent grain uptake	-0.250	-0.100	0.317	0.144	0.263	0.127
Control total uptake	0.476	0.643	0.307	0.300	0.346	0.610
Percent total uptake	-0.050	0.132	0.349	0.190	0.304	0.170

^aAfter 72 hours of soil incubation at 40°C.